

AI-driven Method for Predicting Fibre Orientation in Composites

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Arts et Métiers
Sciences et Technologies

Motivation

Super Discovery 3D printer

❑ Regular printing volume:
1300x2500x1000mm

❑ Capable of printing in out of plane trajectories.

Motivation

Materials

Composite material

- Matrix: ABS
- GF short inclusions

Sanding and polishing
with diamond paste

Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

Methods

Binarization

FIJI/ImageJ:

- Very tedious
- Human errors
- Not very accurate
- Not suitable for measuring a big representative Surface of the material

$$a_{ijk\dots l} = \int p_i p_j p_k \dots p_l \psi(p) dp$$

$$p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2 = 1$$

Advani and Tucker, 1987

Methods

Lila Cai, 2020

$$a_{xx} = a_{11} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sin^2(\beta_i),$$

$$a_{yy} = a_{22} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \cos^2(\beta_i) \sin^2(\varphi_i)$$

$$a_{zz} = a_{33} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \cos^2(\beta_i) \cos^2(\varphi_i)$$

$$\sin \beta = \frac{a}{b}$$

Being:

- a: the diameter of a single glass fiber
- b: length of the long axis of the ellipse
- N: number of glass fibers
- Φ : Orientation angle with respect z and y

Deep Learning Data Augmentation

Variables:

- a: the diameter of a single glass fiber
- b: length of the long axis of the ellipse
- p: % of area occupied by ellipses
- Φ : Orientation angle with respect z and y.

A total of 40000 images generated to train the Neural Network

Parameters adjustment

Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional Neural Network

Convolution + MaxPool

Batch Normalization

$$\hat{x}_i = \frac{x_i - \mu_B}{\sqrt{\sigma_B^2 + \epsilon}}$$

Convolutional Neural Network

Adaptative Pooling

Figure 6. Illustration of adaptive feature pooling on box branch.

$$\text{Output}(c) = \frac{1}{H_{in} \times W_{in}} \sum_{h=1}^{H_{in}} \sum_{w=1}^{W_{in}} \text{Input}(c, h, w) \quad +$$

Flatten to 64 outputs

$$\text{Output} = \sigma(\mathbf{W} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b})$$

Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional Neural Network

ReLU activation function for no-linearity

$$R(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Convolutional Neural Network

Dropout 0.1

Softmax

Deep Learning: Training and Results

Configuration	
Training size	0.8
Validation size	0.1
Test size	0.1
Learnign rate	0.001
Epochs	150
Batch size	16
Loss function	MSE
Optimizer	Adam
Scheduler	On
Training time	4 hour

Deep Learning: Results

Category	Metric	Value
Train Data	Mean Cosine Similarity	0.99953
	Mean Angular Error [°]	1.39502
	Pearson - a_xx	0.99356
Validation Data	Mean Cosine Similarity	0.99951
	Mean Angular Error [°]	1.42294
	Pearson - a_yy	0.99359
Test Data	Mean Cosine Similarity	0.99962
	Mean Angular Error [°]	1.26876
	Pearson - a_zz	0.99453

Metric	Value
JSD_global	0.00023
MAE_global	0.00809
MAPE_global	4.78343
MSE_global	0.00012
R ² _global	0.98937
RMSE_global	0.01108

Real: [0.1104, 0.4132, 0.4764]
 Predicted: [0.1062, 0.4122, 0.4816]
 Mean angular error: 0.56°

Real: [0.0412, 0.8143, 0.1445]
 Predicted: [0.0471, 0.8032, 0.1496]
 Mean angular error: 0.66°

Real: [0.1230, 0.4584, 0.4186]
 Predicted: [0.0900, 0.4633, 0.4467]
 Mean angular error: 3.59°

Real: [0.1464, 0.3999, 0.4537]
 Predicted: [0.1388, 0.4012, 0.4600]
 Mean angular error: 0.85°

Deep Learning: Crossvalidation

5 folds cross-validation

Loss evolution for all folds

	JSD_global	MAE_global	MAPE_global	MSE_global	R ² _global	RMSE_global
Fold_1	0.000217	0.007402	4.782471	0.000183	0.989594	0.011109
Fold_2	0.000275	0.007206	4.784370	0.000100	0.988649	0.011050
Fold_3	0.000253	0.008822	4.784095	0.000122	0.988954	0.011081
Fold_4	0.000240	0.008292	4.782855	0.000113	0.989103	0.011089
Fold_5	0.000196	0.008506	4.782794	0.000199	0.989282	0.011035
Mean	0.000236	0.008046	4.783317	0.000144	0.989116	0.011073
σ	0.00003	0.00071	0.00085	0.00004	0.00035	0.00003

Deep Learning vs Manual Measurement

axx=0.121, ayy=0.698, azz=0.181

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$$\sin \beta = \frac{a}{b}$$

Manual

Weighted average tensor
calculated manually:
[0.11533, 0.78703, 0.09764]

Weighted average tensor:

$$\bar{T} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{z_i} \cdot T_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{z_i}}$$

\bar{T} : Weighted average tensor.

T_i : Tensor corresponding to the i -th image.

z_i : Zoom level of the i -th image.

$\frac{1}{z_i}$: Weight assigned to the i -th image, inversely proportional to the zoom.

N : Total number of images.

Deep Learning

Weighted average tensor
calculated with Deep Learning:
[0.10507, 0.72362, 0.17130]

Mean Angular Error = 6.93°

Workflow

$[a_{xx}, a_{yy}, a_{zz}]$

This process is repeated for each image

Store tensor and corresponding magnification of the image

$$\bar{T} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{z_i} \cdot T_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{z_i}}$$

Weighted Average Orientation Tensor

Generate microstructure and create numerical model in DIGMAT

Conclusions

- Data augmentation techniques are a powerful tool to overcome data scarcity: more than 40000 images generated

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- Finite Elements techniques can be highly improved thanks to Deep Learning techniques allowing to increase the accuracy of digital twins.
- Deep Learning is a super adaptable tool for many applications, where the main 2 difficulties are: Data and enough creativity. Creativity is the limit.

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